

Chichen Itza

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Chichen Itza, located in the Yucatan Peninsula, is a prominent archaeological site that holds great significance in the realm of Mesoamerican studies and the exploration of ancient Maya pre-Hispanic cultures. This ancient city, whose name translates to "At the mouth of the well of the Itza," is a testament to the architectural and cultural prowess of the Maya civilization. Its rich historical and cultural significance has been the subject of extensive scholarly study, with numerous texts and sources contributing to our understanding of this remarkable site. Chichen Itza thrived during the Terminal Classic (Yabnal Phase) and Early Postclassic (Chichen Itza Phase) periods, roughly spanning from the 7th to the 13th century CE. This chronological context places it within a pivotal era of transition and transformation in Maya society, marked by the decline of the southern lowland cities and the emergence of new centers of power in the northern Yucatan. Situated in the northern reaches of the Yucatan Peninsula, Chichen Itza's location played a crucial role in its historical development. The site's proximity to natural water sources and its strategic positioning within the region's trade networks contributed to its prominence as a political and economic hub, influencing the city's growth and cultural interactions with neighboring regions. Chichen Itza's cultural significance extends beyond its architectural grandeur. The site's structures, such as the iconic Pyramid of Kukulcan (El Castillo), the Temple of the Warriors, and the Great Ball Court, or recently excavated Temple of the Turtles in the Initial Serie reflect the Maya's advanced understanding of astronomy, mathematics, and religious practices. Additionally, the integration of diverse architectural styles, believed to be influenced by the Central Mexico people, highlights Chichen Itza's role as a melting pot of Mesoamerican cultures. Chichen Itza's exploration has significantly contributed to the broader field of Mesoamerican studies, shedding light on the interregional connections, sociopolitical dynamics, and religious practices of ancient Maya civilization. As a UNESCO World Heritage site, its preservation and ongoing research serve as a focal point for interdisciplinary studies, encompassing archaeology, anthropology, art history, and epigraphy.

Date Range: 650 CE - 1150 CE

Region: Chichen Itza

Region tags: Chichen Itza, Mexico, Maya Yucatecan Peninsula, Mesoamerica, Maya

This is an estimated map of core city of Chichen Itza. Its extension was estimated around 30 square kilometers. It counted with a lot of peripheral sites, as well as cities under its direct political influence.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Landa, Diego de. *Relación de las cosas de Yucatán*. Porrúa. 1959.
- Source 2: López de Cogolludo, Diego. *Historia de Yucatán*. Barcelona: Linkgua. 2006.
- Source 3: *El libro de los libros de Chilam Balam*. Mexico: Fondo de cultura económica. 1963.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.wayeb.org/download/resources/landa.pdf>
- Source 1 Description: Landa, Diego de. *Relación de las cosas de Yucatán*. Editorial Porrúa. 1959.
- Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/historiadeyucata0000lope/mode/2up>
- Source 2 Description: López de Cogolludo, Diego. *Historia de Yucatán*. Barcelona: Linkgua. 2006.
- Source 3 URL: <https://www.mesoweb.com/chichen/resources/map/EntireMap.html>
- Source 3 Description: The Carnegie Map. Mesoweb. Chichen Itza Resources

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Scientific

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name: The Initial Series Group Project.

Notes: The project began in 1999 under Peter J. Schmidt direction. With the Federal Government PROMEZA program, excavations started again in 2019.

Reference: Osorio León, José Francisco, and Francisco Pérez Ruiz. "Investigaciones recientes en el grupo de la serie inicial en chichén itzá". *Arqueología mexicana*, 2022.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:
– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:
– Year range: 1992-2024

Notes: Under the direction of Peter J. Schmidt

Reference: Schmidt, Peter J.. "Chichén itzá resultados y proyectos nuevos. (1992-1999)". *Arqueología mexicana*, 1999. <https://arqueologiamexicana.mx/mexico-antiguo/chichen-itza-resultados-y-proyectos>.

Reference: Schmidt, Peter J.. "Chichén itzá. poder y esplendor entre la guerra, el comercio y las flores". *Arqueología mexicana*, 2017.

↳ Name of excavation
– Official or descriptive name: Proyecto Chichen Itza

Reference: Morris, Earl Halstead, Ann Axtell Morris, and Jean Charlot. *The temple of the warriors at chichen itza*. Washington D.C.: Carnegie Institute of Washington, 1931. <https://archive.org/details/templeofwarriors02morr/page/n7/mode/2up>.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1924-1934

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: The Temple of the Warriors at Chichen Itza, Yucatan

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Water source

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

– Cave

Notes: Chichen Itza was built over an extended network of underwater rivers and cenotes. Recent studies have shown that the Kukulcan's pyramid was built over a cenote. Recent archaeomagnetic measures made clear that the northern part of Chichen Itza was built over a wide network of cenotes. For example, the Castillo Pyramid was built over a cenote that lies 8 m below the actual floor.

Reference: Sprajc, Ivan, and Pedro Francisco Sánchez Nava. "Astronomía en la arquitectura de chichén itzá: una reevaluación". *Estudios de cultura maya* XLI (2013): 31-60. <https://doi.org/10.19130/iifl.ecm.2013.41.153>.

Reference: Biró, Peter, and Eduardo Pérez de Heredia. "La organización política y el paisaje de chichén itzá, yucatán, México, en el periodo clásico terminal (830-930 dc)". *Latin American antiquity* 29, no. 2 (2018): 207-21. <https://doi.org/10.1017/laq.2017.85>.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Trackway or road-surface

Notes: A complex network of sac'beob or causeways was going through the site and tied Chichen Itza with other cities in Northwest Yucatan peninsula

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:
– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– Yes

- ↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:
– Yes

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Notes: The Carnegie Institute of Washington mapped Chichen Itza from late 1920's to 1950's. The result is available online: <https://www.mesoweb.com/chichen/resources/map/choice.html>

Reference: Casares Contreras, Orlando J.. "Astronomía Y Arquitectura En El Norte De La Península De Yucatán: Análisis Comparativo Entre Chichén Itzá Y Dzibilchaltún" 9, no. 1 (February 4, 2017). <https://doi.org/10.5377/ce.v9i1.3133>.

- ↳ A single structure
– No

- ↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: N/A

- ↳ A group of structures:
– Yes

Notes: Chichen Itza's core is traditionally divided according to two main architectural styles. The northern part of Chichen Itza presents features of Mexican International Style while its southern counterpart has Puuc-Style features.

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

- ↳ A group of features:
– Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The gran nivelation was excavated around the Castillo Pyramid. It revealed platforms and stairs of a former occupation.

Reference: Guida Navarro, Alexandre. "Las serpientes emplumadas de chichén itzá, México, y las etapas de construcción de la gran nivelación". *História*, no. 37 (2018). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1590/1980-4369e2018010>.

Reference: Morris, Earl Halstead, Ann Axtell Morris, and Jean Charlot. *The temple of the warriors at Chichen Itza*. Washington D.C.: Carnegie Institute of Washington, 1931. <https://archive.org/details/templeofwarriors02morr/page/n7/mode/2up>.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The total extension of Chichen Itza is estimated to 30 square kilometers.

Reference: Schmidt, Peter J.. "Birds, ceramics and cacao". In *Twin Tollans. Chichen Itza, Tula and the Epiclassic to Early Postclassic Mesoamerican World*, edited by Jeff Karl Kowalski and Cynthia Kristan-Graham, 2nd ed., 113-55. *Dumbarton Oaks Pre-Columbian Symposia and Colloquia*. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks, 2011.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Notes: It also includes Sacrificial and Political features.

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

↳ In antiquity

– Once

- ↳ In modernity
- Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The painted reliefs of the Lower Temple of the Jaguar depict a ritual with a heavily dressed priest and a solar featured ruler.

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Kukulkan, Sun God Itzmana, Rain God Chaak, Moon Goddess Ixchel, Venus planet

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Council of elders

Notes: The multepal was a council formed by representatives of the different lineages that inhabited the city

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Slaves

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: It is thought by scholars that the Gran nivelación was the water surfaces of the world and that pyramids were mountains that contained seeds like corn, squash and beans.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Yes

↳ What type of scriptures/sacred texts [specify]:

– Type: Calendar tables and astronomical events

↳ Were the scriptures/sacred texts located in a specific room within the main structure:

– Yes

↳ In the cella:

The cella refers to the most interior area of the structure, often where the cult statue(s) might be located.

– Yes

↳ In a restricted section of the structure removed from general traffic:

This would be a back-room or remote part of the structure, i.e. Opisthodomoi in Greek temples, etc

– Yes

↳ Space underneath the structure

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Where are the scriptures/sacred texts located in secondary building:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the scriptures actively used at the place:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Several buildings like the Castillo, the Osario and the Caracol have been designed according to significant astronomical events. They have recently reconsidered in an archaeoastronomical project led by Sprajc and Sánchez Nava.

Reference: Sprajc, Ivan, and Pedro Francisco Sánchez Nava. "Astronomía en la arquitectura de chichén itzá: una reevaluación". *Estudios de cultura maya* XLI (2013): 31-60.
<https://doi.org/10.19130/iifl.ecm.2013.41.153>.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: La Pirámide llamada Castillo o Templo de Kukulcán podría ser una mejor de figurar la montaña sagrada que aparece de manera repetida en la tradición religiosa mesoamericana.

Reference: Casares, Orlando, and Venus Estrella. El Castillo De Chichén Itzá. Su Significado Astronómico, Calendárico Y Agrícola. Yucatán: Maldonado Editores del Mayab, 2020.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As the total surface of Chichen Itza is around 30 square kilometers, there is still a lot to survey and dig. However, the core of the city represents a low percentage of the total inhabited area. Chichen Itza's hinterland is even wider.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 2600

Notes: The Great Ballgame of Chichen Itza is 130 m long and 20 m wide. However, the ballgame also counts with the North and the South building, as well as the Upper and Lower Temple of the Jaguars. So the footprint may be closer to 3000 square meters.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 30

Notes: The Castillo or Pyramid of Kukulcán is the highest monument in Chichen Itza.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The diversity of religious buildings can't allow us to calculate the size of average monument.

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: For the same reason mentioned above.

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– Yes

Notes: Lintels and roof beams were made of zapote wood.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Notes: Lintels of Chichen Itza were made of zapote wood.

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Buildings were made with local limestone.

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

Notes: Buildings were covered with painted low reliefs of the bird-feline-serpent feature like at the Temple of the Warriors (2D8), and three-dimensionnal Feathered Serpent's heads at the bottom of pyramids stairs.

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

Notes: For example, low reliefs were sculpted and painted on the benches of the Great Ballgame, on the Upper Temple of the Jaguars, or at the Monjas Complex.

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: For example, low reliefs of processions have been sculpted on the inner walls and roof of the Lower Temple of the Jaguars (2D1), and on the Mercado benches and altar (3D11).

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– Yes

Notes: For example, the Earth Monster entrance at the annex of the Monjas (4C1).

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

Notes: There are several representations of the Fire Serpent, the Cloud Serpent and the Feathered Serpent.

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: For example, there are several representations of men walking to a central human figure on the Mercado and the 1000 columns benches and altars. Wall paintings at the Temple of the Warriors and the Upper Temple of the Jaguars also represent human beings at the war field. Human beings are also depicted in a procession at the Lower Temple of the Jaguars.

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Felines and Eagles were sculpted on the platform that was named after them. They are also depicted on the frieses of the Upper Temple of the Jaguars. Turtles sculptures were found on the building that wear the same name in the Initial Series complex. Fish are sculpted in low relief between feathered serpents bodies at the Platform of Venus (2D4). The Temple of the Moon (5C11) was named after the relief of a rabbit in a circle relief. There are at least two turtle-shaped at Chichen Itza: one in front the Osario pyramid and the second at the Initial Series complex (5C17). In the very same

complex, shell-shaped reliefs were sculpted on the wall of the Shells House (5C5).

Reference: Osorio León, José Francisco, and Francisco Pérez Ruiz. "Investigaciones recientes en el grupo de la serie inicial en chichén itzá". *Arqueología mexicana*, 2022.

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Hybrid depictions with the bird-feline-serpent-man complex, consisting in a headdress and claws instead of hands, can be observed on the Platform of Venus. On the other hand, the procession reliefs of the Lower Temple of the Jaguars and on the feathered serpent column capitals contain several figures with turtle shells or spiderweb features.

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: A good example is the presence of shields on the Upper Temple of the Jaguars, or at the Platform of the Eagles and of the Jaguars. Year symbol and stars are depicted on the Venus Platform.

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: Flower and plants motifs were painted on the wall of the Upper Temple of the Jaguars, as well as on the benches' reliefs of the Great Ballgame. There are also depictions of the ceiba and cacao trees among others.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: Schmidt noted that hieroglyphic texts are scarce among structures. However, graphemes names have been observed besides human depictions at the Temple of the Warriors. They might have been read in Maya. The longest inscriptions have been registered at the Osario and on the Stela 2 of the Casa Colarada.

Reference: Schmidt, Peter J. "Birds, ceramics and cacao". In *Twin tollans. chichen itza, tula and the epiclassic to early postclassic mesoamerican world*, edited by Jeff Karl Kowalski and Cynthia Kristan-Graham, 2nd ed., 113-55. *Dumbarton oaks pre-columbian symposia and colloquia*. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks, 2011.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– Yes

Notes: Wall paintings of the Upper Temple of the Jaguars or the altar prepared inside the cella of the Temple of the Warriors might have been available only for the ruling elites of Chichen Itza.

- ↳ Can the decoration be revealed:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - Yes

- ↳ Cult statues:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:
 - Yes

- ↳ Statues of humans:
 - Yes

Notes: For example, standard-bearers and chacmool sculptures are available in the northern part of the site, at the Temple of the Warriors (2D8). In the Puuc-style Initial Series Complex, the Palace of the Phalli (5C14) was called for the presence of human phalli sculptures. A kneeling man sculpture has been recently discovered in the main patio of the Shells House (5C5). It was a part of the Eastern wall features that collapsed.

Reference: Ruppert, Karl. Chichén Itzá. architectural notes and plans. Washington D.C.: Carnegie Institute of Washington, 1952.

Reference: Morris, Earl Halstead, Ann Axtell Morris, and Jean Charlot. The temple of the warriors at Chichén Itzá. Washington D.C.: Carnegie Institute of Washington, 1931. <https://archive.org/details/templeofwarriors02morr/page/n7/mode/2up>.

Reference: Osorio León, José Francisco, and Francisco Pérez Ruiz. "Investigaciones recientes en el grupo de la serie inicial en Chichén Itzá". *Arqueología mexicana*, 2022.

- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: N/A

- ↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

- Yes

Notes: Generally speaking, almost all architectural reliefs at Chichén Itzá were also stuccoed and painted with vivid colors.

Reference: Ruppert, Karl. Chichén Itzá. architectural notes and plans. Washington D.C.: Carnegie Institute of Washington, 1952.

- ↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

Notes: According to Stuart in Schmidt (2011), the inscription of the Castillo of Old Chichén might be related to an origin myth.

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: As there are plenty of examples, we could mention the recently discovered Captives Altar found at the Shells House (5C5): 34 human beings have their hands tied on their back.

Reference: Osorio León, José Francisco, and Francisco Pérez Ruiz. "Investigaciones recientes en el grupo de la serie inicial en chichén itzá". *Arqueología mexicana*, 2022.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the wall paintings remains can be observed in the inner room of the Upper Temple of the Jaguars (2D1). They represent several battefields.

Reference: McVicker, Mary. *Adela breton A victorian artist amid mexico's ruins*. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 2005.

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase, and Orrin C. Shane III. *Cenote of sacrifice; maya treasures from the sacred well at chichén itzá*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1984.

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

Reference: Morris, Earl Halstead, Ann Axtell Morris, and Jean Charlot. *The temple of the warrios at chichen itza*. Washington D.C.: Carnegie Institute of Washington, 1931. <https://archive.org/details/templeofwarriors02morr/page/n7/mode/2up>.

Reference: McVicker, Mary. *Adela breton A victorian artist amid mexico's ruins*. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 2005.

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase, and Orrin C. Shane III. *Cenote of sacrifice; maya treasures from the sacred well at chichén itzá*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1984.

↳ Type

– Secco

Notes: All inner walls of the Upper Temple of the Jaguars were painted. The substructure of the Temple of the Warriors also contained painted walls, columns and reliefs.

Reference: McVicker, Mary. *Adela breton A victorian artist amid mexico's ruins*. Albuquerque: University of New Mexico Press, 2005.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
– Yes

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
– Yes

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there mosaics present:
– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
– Yes

Reference: Schmidt, Peter J. "Birds, ceramics and cacao". In Twin tollans. chichen itza, tula and the epiclassic to early postclassic mesoamerican world, edited by Jeff Karl Kowalski and Cynthia Kristan-Graham, 2nd ed., 113-55. Dumbarton oaks pre-columbian symposia and colloquia. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks , 2011.

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
– No
Notes: Inscriptions are always meaningful.

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]
– Yes

Notes: They may name individuals or relate mythological information, as for the Osorio one, deciphered by Stuart.

Reference: Schmidt, Peter J.. "Birds, ceramics and cacao". In Twin tollans. chichen itza, tula and the epiclassic to early postclassic mesoamerican world, edited by Jeff Karl Kowalski and Cynthia Kristan-Graham, 2nd ed., 113-55. Dumbarton oaks pre-columbian symposia and colloquia. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks , 2011.

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]
–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Stuccoed walls

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase, and Orrin C. Shane III. *Cenote of sacrifice; maya treasures from the sacred well at chichén itzá*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1984.

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase. *Artifacts from the cenote of sacrifice, chichén itzá, yucatán*. *Memoirs of the peabody museum of archaeology & ethnology*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1992.

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: As the Feathered Serpent. Its representations flourish at Chichen Itza, particularly in the Toltec called part of the city. There is also an iconographic complex called Bird-Feline-Serpent-Human complex, as it can be observed at the Platform of Venus in the Puuc-style part of the city.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: The pawahtuns can be represented as elderly men. It was common to represent human beings wearing animal attributes like birdpeaks or turtle shells

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: They can be painted, for example at the Upper Temple of the Jaguars walls. But they are mainly sculpted, as it can be observed with the chacmool (human shaped sacrificial altar) or dressed as warriors at the Temple of the Warriors and Temple of the Big Tables colonnades or on the reliefs of the Great Ballgame benches. In the Initial Series Group, they are also plenty of

human sculpted reliefs on columns or outer walls (Temple of the Phalli, for example).

Reference: Ringle, William. "Who Was Who in Ninth-century Chichen Itza". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 1, no. 2 (1990): 233–43. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0956536100000250>.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

Notes: Wall paintings of the Upper Temple of the Jaguars depict several battle scenes. A painted wall fragment of the sub-structure of the Temple of the Warriors (2D8) represent canoes with armed warriors on the sea. On the upper part of the painting, a procession of prisoners cross a village and come to a Feathered Serpent building.

Reference: Ringle, William. "Who Was Who in Ninth-century Chichen Itza". *Ancient Mesoamerica* 1, no. 2 (1990): 233–43. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0956536100000250>.

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase, and Orrin C. Shane III. *Cenote of sacrifice; maya treasures from the sacred well at chichén itzá*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1984.

Reference: Morris, Earl Halstead, Ann Axtell Morris, and Jean Charlot. *The temple of the warriors at chichen itza*. Washington D.C.: Carnegie Institute of Washington, 1931. <https://archive.org/details/templeofwarriors02morr/page/n7/mode/2up>.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– No

↳ Cannibalism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– Yes

Notes: Sacrificed human victims were thrown to the water of the Great Cenote at the North of the site.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– Field doesn't know

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– Yes

Notes: Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, and meaningful symbolic value

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

Notes: Some Feathered Serpent representations accompanied rulers' representations, as it can be seen in the wall paintings of the Upper Temple of the Jaguars, on the painted reliefs of the Lower Temple of the Jaguars and on the Mercado reliefs.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Reference: Baudez, Claude-François. *Una historia de la religión maya*. Mexico City: Centro de estudios mexicanos y centroamericanos, 2004. <https://books.openedition.org/cemca/948>.

Reference: Velázquez García, Erik. *Morada De Dioses. Los Componentes Anímicos Del Cuerpo Humano Entre Los Mayas Clásicos*. Mexico City: Fondo de cultura económica, 2023.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Only with certain elite individuals, as it can be seen on the Lower Temple of the Jaguars painted reliefs. The main character seems to communicate with a feathered serpent whose body seems to serve as a sacrificial stone/altar.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:
– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:
– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:
– Yes

↳ In dreams:
– Yes

↳ In trance possession:
– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:
– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:
– I don't know

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be seen:
– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine spirits can be physically felt:
– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

- ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - I don't know
- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):
– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:
– Yes

- ↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Libations:
 - Yes [specify]: honey, liquor, human and animal blood
 - ↳ Offerings of food:
 - Yes [specify]: Tamales

↳ Animal sacrifice:
– Yes [specify]: deer, fish, peccari, turkey

↳ Human sacrifice:
– Yes [specify]: Decapitation scenes sculpted on the Great Ballgame benches. Human remains were actually found by dragging the bottom of the Great cenote. Victims were grown men and women, as well as children. Actually 60% of the victims found in the Cenote were children or subadults. 68% were male individuals.

Reference: de Anda, Guillermo. "Los huesos del cenote sagrado de chichén itzá, yucatán". *Arqueología mexicana* XIV, no. 83 (2007): 54-57.
<https://arqueologiamexicana.mx/mexico-antiguo/los-huesos-del-cenote-sagrado-de-chichen-itza-yucatan>.

↳ Sacred objects:
– Yes [specify]: vessels, jadeites plaque, pendants, carved globes; wood earflare, sticks, and atlatl; fired clay vessel; gold disks, crescents, etc.

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase. *Artifacts from the cenote of sacrifice, chichén itzá, yucatán*. *Memoirs of the peabody museum of archaeology & ethnology*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1992.

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase, and Orrin C. Shane III. *Cenote of sacrifice; maya treasures from the sacred well at chichén itzá*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1984.

↳ Daily life objects:
– Yes [specify]: axes, sickle-like tools, baskets, spindle whorles, weaving tools

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase. *Artifacts from the cenote of sacrifice, chichén itzá, yucatán*. *Memoirs of the peabody museum of archaeology & ethnology*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1992.

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase, and Orrin C. Shane III. *Cenote of sacrifice; maya treasures from the sacred well at chichén itzá*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1984.

↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: Copal and tobacco smoke

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:
– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:
– No

↳ Other:
– Other [specify]: N/A

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:
– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: Estimation impossible to do.

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Frequency non available.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Yes

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:
– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:
– Yes [specify]: Turkey, jaguars, turtles

Notes: Animal bones have been found in the Cenote (sinkhole) of sacrifices.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:
– Yes

↳ Adults
– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:
– Male
– Female

↳ Children
– Yes

↳ Is biological sex available from evidence:
– Other/InD

↳ Foreigners and/or slaves
– I don't know

↳ Elites
– I don't know

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Yes [specify]: Wall painting of the Temple of the Warriors substructure show a procession of captives. Their bodies are painted with horizontal red and white stripes. Their hands are tied on their back. Comparing with other pre-Hispanic representations, these characters are going to be sacrificed.

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Yes

↳ Suicide

– No

↳ Bloodletting

– Yes

Notes: As suggested by Millet, bloodletting may have taken place in front, in and around the Great Ballcourt and other locations.

Reference: Miller, Virginia E. "Representaciones De Sacrificio En Chichén Itzá". In *Antropología De La Eternidad : La Muerte En La Cultura Maya*, edited by Andrés Ciudad Ruiz, María Josefa Iglesias Ponce de León , and Mario Humberto Ruz, 7:383–404. Publicaciones De Las Sociedad Española De Estudios Mesoamericanos. Madrid: Sociedad española de estudios Mayas, 2003.

↳ Mutilation

– I don't know

↳ Is self-sacrifice common and/or expect of elites:

– Yes

↳ Is it an elite prerogative:

– No

↳ Is it a kingship prerogative:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase. *Artifacts from the cenote of sacrifice, chichén itzá, yucatán. Memoirs of the peabody museum of archaeology & ethnology*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 1992.

Reference: Coggins, Clemency Chase, and Orrin C. Shane III. *Cenote of sacrifice; maya treasures from the sacred well at chichén itzá*. Austin: University of Texas Press, 1984.

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

↳ By specific individuals

–Yes [specify]: Rulers and representatives of the lineages.

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– I don't know

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– I don't know

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
– I don't know

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:
– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:
– I don't know

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):
– Yes

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
– I don't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– I don't know

Are festivals present:

– Yes

↳ Frequency of festivals
– specify: According to solar and venusian calendar.

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
– Elites
– Non-elites
– Only locals

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
– Yes

↳ Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:
– I don't know

↳ Requires new construction/decoration of the place:
– Yes

↳ Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– I don't know

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
– number: unknown

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
– I don't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

↳ Divination by examination of the exta:
Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species
– I don't know

↳ Divination through human communication:
– I don't know

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
– I don't know

↳ Divination through non-living material:
– Other [specify in comments]
Notes: We don't have any clue about it.

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

- ↳ Present full time
 - Yes
- ↳ Present part time
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:
 - Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:
– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:
– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

- ↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:
 - Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

- ↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Does this place lease out land:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Does this place lease out tools:
 - Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

- ↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
 - Yes

- ↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
 - Yes

- ↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
 - Yes

- ↳ Function for water management:
 - Yes

- ↳ Part of the transportation network:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Reference: Grube, Nikolai, and Ruth Krochock. "Reading between the lines: hieroglyphic texts from chichen itza and its neighbors". In Twin tollans. chichén itzá, tula and the epiclassic to early postclassic mesoamerican world, edited by Jeff Karl Kowalski and Cynthia Kristan-Graham, 1st ed.. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks Research library and Collection, 2007.

https://www.academia.edu/43514341/Reading_between_the_Lines_Hieroglyphic_Texts_from_Chichen_Itza_and_its_Ne

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– Yes

Reference: Schmidt, Peter J. "Birds, ceramics and cacao". In Twin tollans. chichen itza, tula and the epiclassic to early postclassic mesoamerican world, edited by Jeff Karl Kowalski and Cynthia Kristan-Graham, 2nd ed., 113-55. Dumbarton oaks pre-columbian symposia and colloquia. Washington, D.C.: Dumbarton Oaks , 2011.

↳ Attached to the structures as decoration:

– Yes

↳ Housed within the place/structure:

– Yes

↳ As dedicatory inscription(s):

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

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